

VOICE USER INTERFACES FOR CONTROL SYSTEM AND EXPERIMENT CONTROL

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Abstract

Voice-user interfaces (VUI) use speech recognition technology to enable user interaction with technology. Virtual assistants like Siri, Google Home and Alexa have popularized them. The creation of useful VUIs requires the deep understanding of human communication. This manuscript presents a panorama of VUIs and an analysis of the key features needed in order to use them efficiently for Machine and Experiment Control Systems typically used in research infrastructures. Mycroft [1,2] is a leading open source voice assistant that is highly customizable. Tango [3] is an Open Source solution for Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition systems (SCADA) and Distributed Control Systems (DCS). The second part of the manuscript presents and discuss the integration of Mycroft and Tango based control systems for applications in Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste (including experiment control). The potentialities and weakness of the solution, like command uncertainty, are presented as challenges. This integration may inspire novel ways of interactions and new developments of interfaces for accelerators, beam lines and large experimental physics control systems.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of this pilot project is to enhance the user experience in interfacing with a TANGO Control System [3] by introducing a voice assistant. For beam line users, machine operators and staff of the research infrastructures in general is much easier and faster to retrieve information from and send commands to the control system respectively via voice. The basic idea is to allow the users (hereinafter the term “user” will refer to a general user of the software) to interact with the devices installed in the facility using the natural language and for example retrieve the value of a measurement, know the status of a device or open and close a complex system like a beam line using voice. This means that we need to integrate the voice assistant system and the TANGO control system. In order to achieve this goal Mycroft AI [1] was chosen as the target voice assistant system.

MYCROFT VOICE ASSISTANT

Mycroft AI is an open source voice assistant system, written in python, available on Github [2] and supported by a well-organized community. It is lightweight and also for this reason it can run on several platforms and hardware like a Raspberry Pi, an Andorid device or a Linux desktop. The software is modular and allows freedom, flexibility and control over how the voice assistant works. Mycroft architecture and its components are described in (Fig. Mycroft Architecture):

- Wake word detection is the assistant ‘entry point’, the users has to say a customizable special word to tell Mycroft that he is about to issue a command.
- Speech to Text (STT) is the software component that takes spoken words and turn them into text.
- Intent parser is the software component that identifies the user’s intent based on the text contents.
- Text to speech (TTS) is the software component that takes a text and translate it into a speech that can be pronounced as voice.
- Middleware is the software component that acts as a software bus, named mycroft-core and is a sort of the ‘glue’ between the different modules while the Mycroft’s Home and API is the platform that hold users and device information.
- Skills can be considered as plug-ins, a piece of software that add functionalities to the assistant.

The first four components of the list can be ‘swapped out’ for others, for example the TTS software could be Mimic (default), GoogleTTS, MaryTTS, eSpeak or FATTs as well. Almost all the software runs on the device in which Mycroft is installed, but there is a part of the software that runs on the server side like the STT module and others services including those used in order to store users or device settings. This server, named Mycroft’s Home, runs externally, its services are reachable on the internet and executed on the Mycroft Cloud but soon the Mycroft team will release the server code on Github allowing a complete independent Mycroft installation.

Figure 1: Mycroft architecture.

Skill

Skill is a common concept in the world of the voice assistants. As said above the skill represents a specific functionality of the voice assistant and, in practice, is a self-contained part of the software code developed for a specific purpose by the Mycroft team or the community of developers. This code has some entry points, that is, one or more python functions, named intent handler, that Mycroft Core can call in case it matches the user *intent*. These handlers can access to the user's *utterance* in case it is needed to execute their task.

Mycroft Workflow

A user who wants to interact with the assistant at first has to say the *wake word*. Once this word has been detected, Mycroft will wait for an *utterance* pronounced, that is, a command or a question. The user has to say a phrase that will be parsed by Mycroft in order to interpret the user *intent* hence find the skill to accomplish the requested task.

PILOT IMPLEMENTATION

In order to make Mycroft interfaceable with TANGO a specific skill was developed. This *tango-skill* along with Mycroft have been installed in a workstation running Xubuntu 18.04 LTS desktop x86_64; *TANGO 9.3.3 libraries* and the python modules *pytango* [4] and *jellyfish* [5] were installed as well. Fig. 2 shows the components of the implementation schema with Mycroft and TANGO entities.

Figure 2: Implementation schema.

Tango Skill

The skill allows to read a TANGO device attribute (hereinafter referred to as “attribute”), repeat the last read, send commands and update the aliases configuration which will be described more clearly later on. Once Mycroft matches the intent with the “tango-skill”, the corresponding handler will be executed. In case of an attribute read, the words which compose the name of the attribute requested by the

user will be extracted by the user’s utterance. One of the extracted words identifies the location in which the device from which the user wants to read an attribute is installed; if Mycroft can’t find the location in the user’s utterance it will ask the user to repeat the name of the location. These keywords will be matched against a list of preconfigured attribute aliases which map the real attributes. The choice of using aliases come from the fact that the attributes are identified by a string composed of abbreviation with an uncertain meaning and that has to follow the TANGO name structure (family/domain/member/attribute); these T. name are not suitable for the common speech, furthermore it’s hard for a STT module to detect acronym and abbreviation. The skill will therefore call a TANGO *read_attribute* to retrieve the value requested by the user and will tell its value and where appropriate further information such as its warning or alarm state. The analysed case is about a read of an attribute but the behaviour is similar even in case the user’s request is a command, except for the necessity of a confirm by the user to proceed with the operation proposed by Mycroft. The skill supports English and Italian language but can easily be extended to support other languages as well.

Matching Going back to the case of the *intent* handler that allows to retrieve an attribute value, the skill will try to extract from the user’s *utterance* all the keywords useful for the matching of the attribute alias that maps the attribute requested by the user. This extraction is actually a filtering operation in which the words that are considered not noteworthy like articles, adverbs and so on are excluded. The location is a main keyword that it’s used to select a subset of aliases against which the keywords will be matched. An alias is in practice a sequence of words (expressed in natural language) point separated, that refer to a specific attribute, e.g. “penning.pressure.frontend”. Misunderstanding is taken into account; it might happen that STT modules can’t turn correctly the user’s speech to text, for this reason the matching operation involves string comparisons methods like *Jaro-Winkler* distance and *Match rating approach* [6]. In the end the matching process will assign a reliability value to each alias, that is, a measurement of how confident is the skill that the attribute to which that alias refers is what the user wants to read. An alias is matched if its reliability value exceeds a defined threshold, in case more than one alias’ are matched you can ask Mycroft to list all of them.

Configuration It’s clear that in order to make it usable the skill has to know the list of the attribute aliases, the linked attributes and the location where the physical device is installed. All this information is stored in the TANGO database(s) as *free properties*. An attribute stored in a T. database belong certainly to a T. devices of the control system referenced by the database itself. As shown in Table 1, the property values follow a specific structure, in order to parse it easily, e.g. “*elettra_(en-us)penning.pressure,(it-it)pressione.di.penning,elettra/vac/vgpe.01/press*”. At the beginning there is the location where the real device is installed, then there are descriptions in natural language of

the attribute, with a prefix used to determine the language and the last part identifies the attribute.

Table 1: TANGO Free Property (w = word, loc = location, d/f/m/a-c = domain/family/member/attribute-command, []+ = one or more occurrences)

Property name	Value
attrs	loc ₁ _(en-us).[w.]+,(it-it).[w.]+,d/f/m/a ₁
	loc ₁ _(en-us).[w.]+,(it-it).[w.]+,d/f/m/a ₂
	...
cmds	loc ₂ _(en-us).[w.]+,(it-it).[w.]+,d/f/m/c ₁
	...

Another information requested is the list of the *TANGO_HOSTS* of all controls systems in which are configured the *free properties* used by the voice assistant. This list has to be inserted in the *skill settings* which can be done via web on Mycroft’s Home site. Summing up there are two configuration points, on the TANGO side you have to insert in the *free property* the aliases of attributes and commands of the device that you want to manage using the voice assistant and on the Mycroft web side you have to insert the list of the *TANGO_HOSTS* involved.

Use Case

A possible scenario is that a beam scientist wants to start an in-house experiment, Mycroft is installed in a workstation of the beamline. The scientist before starting the acquisition has to open the beamline lightpath. After the wake word he/she just says “Open the *<name of the beamline>*”. Mycroft asks him/her for a confirmation, after which it sends the command to the TANGO control system.

LIMITS AND PROBLEMS

The voice assistant can misunderstand the users’ request and this could be annoying to the users and can lead to a loss of trust in the assistant.

As the voice assistant will be more and more used, hence more and more T. device commands and attributes will be inserted in the system, it might be that the matching algorithm doesn’t fit all the use cases, which means that fulfilling the needs of many users can be hard. Moreover, there is a security aspect that should be taken into account: any person that can be heard by Mycroft could potentially send commands to the control system.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

In order put the system into full production it is necessary to improve the matching algorithm to make it more precise and more capable to interpret correctly the user’s request. Another possible improvement we planning is to add some functionalities the tango-skill such as the possibility to set a value of an attribute.

An extensive use of the system in the field will permit to evaluate users feedback and further improve the voice user interface to the control system.

CONCLUSION

We have presented a VUI integrated in a Machine and Experiment Control Systems of a research infrastructure. The system is based on Mycroft, an open source voice assistant that is highly customizable which has been integrated in the Tango Distributed Control System. We have discussed the potentialities and weakness of the solution. This integration may inspire novel ways of interactions and new developments of interfaces for accelerators, beam lines and large experimental physics control systems. We see in this system a great potential to make the users life easier but some problems and risks have to be considered in order to exploit the full potential of this solution.

REFERENCES

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